

Ionic Neuromodulation For Epilepsy Treatment (IN-FET)

A Data Management Plan

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Project webpage: <https://www.in-fet.org>

Project abstract:

The IN-FET project ultimately aims at a breakthrough biocompatible neuromodulation technology, relevant for future brain implants for epilepsy treatment, advancing neuroscience, biomedical microsystems engineering, and nano-neurotechnology. IN-FET's vision is to alter fundamental biophysical properties of excitable nerve cells and of their communications by direct ionic actuation at the microscopic scale, while monitoring cell responses by arrays of nanoscale transistors. Development and testing proceed *in vitro*, by the use of electroactive polymers to trap/release specific ions in the extracellular milieu.

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Initial DMP

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose

Data generation aims at enabling design, fabrication, testing, characterisation, and biological experimental validation of novel microsystems (based on nanoelectronics and ion-selective polymeric actuation) for modulating the bioelectric activity of excitable nerve cells.

1.2 Data created and shared internally

Data generated in WP1 and WP4 consist in

- device micro- and nanofabrication designs,
- their electronic testing and validation, as well as
- their electrochemical characterisation.

Data will specifically include (a) computer-aided design binary files, (b) preliminary numerical results on distribution of electrical voltages/currents as well as ionic species concentrations, obtained from device-level software simulators, and (c) their real-time measurements in actual hardware fabricated Si- and polymeric-based devices.

These are all sensitive data, in terms of Intellectual Property Rights and patenting. Thus, access to WP1,4 data will be restricted to the consortium partners involved in the work and will not be shared externally or uploaded to public data repositories.

1.3 Data created, re-used internally and shared publicly

Data generated in WP2 and WP3 consist in

- *in silico* numerical simulations of mathematical models and
- *in vitro* electrophysiological recordings from neurobiological experiments.

These will specifically include (a) ASCII text files describing the code of simulations, (b) Jupyter notebook files combining model equations, code, and figures generated, (c) ASCII text files or binary files describing the time series of simulated traces as well as of actual biosignals detected and recorded in electrophysiological measurements.

These data generate knowledge (i.e. insights, analytical workflows, experimental protocols, troubleshooting instructions, feedback on design improvements for WP1,4) and are internally shared and re-used within the IN-FET consortium.

We will subscribe to Zenodo, where we will upload our scientific production, with initially restricted access open for the members of the consortium. Uploaded data will become openly accessible after the publication of the corresponding scientific papers.

1.3.1 Simulations, *in silico* work

Mathematical model equations of electrical/ion transport, diffusion, capture into the polymers, as well as related computer code to simulate them on a computer, will be developed by IUNET and UNIGE. These will guide design and operation of the sensing and actuation devices to alter and modulate the electrophysiological behavior of neurons.

The generation of such data represents the deliverables D2.1-2.4, that are propaedeutic to the work carried out in WP3.

The size of the files uploaded can greatly vary and range from few KBs to several MBs. [Github.com](https://github.com) will be used as a repository for code and data, to be replicated in a [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org) repository (i.e. through the [auto-sync function \(https://guides.github.com/activities/citable-code/\)](https://guides.github.com/activities/citable-code/), linking Github to Zenodo).

1.3.2 Experimental, *in vitro* work

SISSA's experimental neurobiological work aims at validating WP1,4 devices, integrating WP2's simulation predictions. Experimental data generated will consist of electrical voltage and current traces of the spontaneous and evoked electrical activity of neurons and networks of neurons, generating

- experimental protocols for cell culturing, integrated with WP1,4 devices (text files)
- analytical workflows (text files)
- records of neuronal activities (text files, graphs as PDF files)
- feedback (text files) to WP1,4 aiming at device performances optimization
- Deliverables D3.1-3.4

All data are going to be shared on [Github.com](https://github.com) and [Zenodo.org](https://zenodo.org), with restricted access limited to the consortium members. A subset of protocols and voltage/current recorded traces associated with the publication of scientific papers will be shared publicly. The size of each data file will be ranging from few MBs to few GBs.

2. FAIR data

2.1 General considerations

Following [Force11 \(https://www.force11.org/datacitationprinciples\)](https://www.force11.org/datacitationprinciples) principles, we refer to a **data object** as the combination of digital data elements, their metadata, and a series of unique identifiers (DOIs). The latter is issued with every register/published data element on Zenodo, together with detailed provenance of each element thus making all data uploaded traceable to a registered Zenodo user. Every data element and metadata will have a clear indication of its release version, with metadata describing and annotating the content, format, meaning of corresponding data element(s). Metadata files will contain a minimum of three keywords, to facilitate the automated/unsupervised discoverability of data elements in our repositories, further including the definition of special vocabulary or acronyms. All metadata stored in Zenodo will comply with JSON-formatting. Finally, metadata will contain the following:

- DOI of the data elements it refers to;
- Date Publication + Release Date in ISO 8601 standard;
- Title;
- Author or Creator;
- Creator Identifier: ORCID6 or other unique identifier of the individual creator;
- Contact information;
- Description;
- Related Scientific Publication, if any;
- Subject;
- Size of the file;
- Type of file;

- Methods or software tools to access the data;
- Deposit date;
- Depositor;
- Version;
- License under which access to the content is provided.

2.1 Making data openly accessible

Files will be deposited to Zenodo in restricted records, initially restricting public access until official approval of the owner. Protected hyperlinks to files under embargo will be shared with the reviewers of manuscript submitted for consideration at open access journals. The embargo will be automatically lifted when the associated paper is published.

In fact, data will be considered sensitive until publication and initially only accessible to consortium users. Upon publication, terms of use will be specified with a clear indication on how to cite the data for re-use. The simplest and most widely adopted file standards (e.g. text files) will be privileged on vendors lock-in alternatives. Data will be accessible by the most common available tools (e.g. Microsoft Office Word, PowerPoint, Excel, Acrobat Reader, Adobe Illustrator, etc.). Whenever special or custom tools are required to access data, this will be clearly pointed out and carefully described in the metadata.

Metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Textual items, descriptions of procedures and protocols and explanation accompanying and documenting the data will be written in English, using a formal, accessible, and broadly applicable style for knowledge representation. In case special vocabulary or acronyms are used, these will be defined in the associated metadata. For certain terms we may refer to open, external vocabularies (e.g. the open definition of a given use license, the reference to the funders and grants, through OpenAIRE). When included, each referenced external piece of metadata will be qualified by a resolvable URL address.

Finally, standard text files will be used for the largest majority of numerical simulations and data analysis scripts, which will also consist of Jupyter notebooks, combining together textual explanations, code, and figures generated by the code.

The JSON schema of Zenodo will be adopted as internal representation of metadata, enabling the ease of exporting them to other popular formats (e.g. Dublin Core, MARCXML, etc.).

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

The restricted access is needed during the lifetime of the IN-FET project, until complete publication of all results in scientific (open-access) journals. However, aiming data accessibility prior to publication, biorxiv or arxiv may be used. All released public data will be made available to third parties for re-use. The quality of the data is assured first by revisions, internal to the consortium, and then by the peer-review process of the manuscripts associated. Once publicly available, data will be re-usable indefinitely.

3. Allocation of resources

In the IN-FET consortium, each partner has allocated ~5k€/yr for dissemination through open-access journals and platforms. Data management charges and duties are a common

responsibility for all members of the IN-FET consortium. Long-term preservation will be facilitated by the choice of standard and open file format (i.e. text-files) and benefit from the long-term preservation strategies of Zenodo.

4. Data security

Data files and metadata posted at Zenodo will be redundantly stored online and offline, as independent replicas, for the lifetime of the repository, representing the lifetime of Zenodo's host lab at CERN. This is associated with an experimental programme, currently defined for a very long-time horizon during the next 20 years. All data files are stored in CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis. The members of the consortium will locally host portions of the data generated in institutional cloud servers or network attached storage RAID systems.

5. Ethical aspects

Ethical aspects regarding data generation are solely associated with the neurobiological *in vitro* experimental activities at SISSA. Such activities have been officially authorised by the Italian Ministry of Health and are supervised by an institutional animal welfare institutional committee at SISSA.

6. Other

At each partner, institutional or departmental practices and procedures for data preservation are in place. These will complement, but not replace the official procedures described in the present document.